

Redefining orofacial rehabilitation for transformative clinical outcomes.

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Abstract

Orofacial rehabilitation is a cornerstone in restoring function, aesthetics, and quality of life for individuals affected by congenital anomalies, trauma, or disease. While conventional approaches have achieved significant milestones, the evolving demands of personalized care and advancements in technology necessitate redefining the boundaries of this field. This review explores the transformative potential of innovative techniques and materials in orofacial rehabilitation, with a focus on bridging existing gaps and envisioning future possibilities.

The integration of cutting-edge technologies such as 3D printing, CAD/CAM systems, and artificial intelligence has revolutionized precision and customization in prosthetic fabrication. Concurrently, advancements in biomimetic materials, biopolymers, and nanotechnology offer new avenues for enhancing durability, functionality, and patient comfort. The emergence of regenerative medicine, including tissue engineering and stem cell therapies, further highlights the potential for restoring biological structures rather than merely replacing them.

The clinical implications of these innovations, emphasize their role in improving patient outcomes, addressing current challenges, and fostering interdisciplinary collaboration. It also examines the ethical and sustainability aspects of incorporating novel solutions into clinical practice. Finally, it identifies promising research directions, including the role of artificial intelligence, genetic influences, and eco-friendly practices in shaping the future of orofacial rehabilitation.

By reimagining traditional practices and embracing innovation this approach aims to inspire clinicians, researchers, and educators to push the boundaries of orofacial rehabilitation.

Keywords: 3D printing, Artificial Intelligence, CAD/CAM, Orofacial rehabilitation.

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Introduction

Orofacial rehabilitation is essential for restoring not only the functional aspects of the oral and facial structures but also the aesthetic and psychosocial well-being of individuals affected by various conditions.^[1] The orofacial region is intricately linked to critical functions such as mastication, speech, and facial expression, all of which are fundamental to daily life and social interaction.^[2] Beyond functionality, the aesthetics of the orofacial region significantly influence an individual's self-esteem and societal perceptions.

Restoring these functions and appearances provides patients with a sense of normalcy, dignity, and confidence, making orofacial rehabilitation a cornerstone of modern healthcare.^[3,4]

The importance of orofacial rehabilitation has grown with the increasing complexity of cases arising from congenital anomalies, trauma, oncologic surgeries, and degenerative diseases.^[5] Conventional approaches, while effective to an extent, have often been limited by their inability to fully address the unique needs of each patient. These methods are

frequently constrained by the availability of materials, the precision of fabrication techniques, and the adaptability of designs to changing patient anatomies.^[6] For instance, creating prosthetic devices that seamlessly integrate with a patient's facial features while maintaining functionality and durability remains a significant challenge. Similarly, traditional surgical and prosthetic techniques often struggle to replicate the intricate symmetry and dynamics of the orofacial region. Another limitation exist in the static nature of many conventional solutions.^[7] Orofacial structures, particularly in young or growing patients, are dynamic and subject to ongoing changes. Prosthetic devices designed using traditional methods may fail to accommodate these changes, necessitating frequent replacements or adjustments. This not only places an additional financial burden on patients but also impacts their overall rehabilitation experience. Additionally, the biocompatibility and aesthetic matching of materials used in conventional methods often provide space for improvement. Patients frequently report dissatisfaction with the appearance, comfort, or longevity of traditional prosthetics, highlighting the need for more advanced solutions.^[8] The advent of new technologies and materials has created opportunities to overcome these limitations and revolutionize orofacial rehabilitation. Innovations such as 3D printing and CAD/CAM systems allow for the precise replication of complex anatomical structures, enabling the fabrication of prosthetics that are tailored to each patient's unique anatomy. Unlike traditional methods, these digital workflows streamline the design and production process, reducing errors and improving the fit and functionality of prosthetic devices.^[9,10] Furthermore, advancements in imaging technologies, such as cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), have

enhanced the ability to visualize and plan interventions with unparalleled accuracy.

The development of biomimetic materials represents transformative advancement in orofacial rehabilitation. These materials mimic the properties of natural tissues, offering improved biocompatibility, strength, and aesthetic integration.^[11,12] Nanotechnology-infused polymers and composites, provide enhanced durability and resistance to wear, ensuring that prosthetics maintain their functionality over longer periods. Regenerative medicine, including tissue engineering and stem cell applications, adds another dimension by focusing on the restoration of biological structures rather than their replacement. By leveraging the body's inherent healing mechanisms, these approaches have the potential to achieve outcomes that were previously unimaginable.^[13,14]

The shift towards artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning, making significant contributions to orofacial rehabilitation. These technologies enable predictive modeling and treatment optimization, allowing clinicians to develop highly personalized rehabilitation plans. AI algorithms can analyze a patient's anatomical and functional data to recommend the best prosthetic design or surgical approach. Moreover, AI-assisted workflows can enhance the precision of complex procedures, reducing complications and improving outcomes.^[14-16]

In addition to technological advancements, there is an increasing emphasis on the aesthetic and cultural aspects of orofacial rehabilitation. The ability to customize prosthetics to match a patient's skin tone, facial features, and personal preferences is becoming a critical aspect of care. This not only improves patient satisfaction but also addresses the psychological and social dimensions of rehabilitation. For patients, the restoration of their facial features often marks

a return to societal participation and improved quality of life.^[17]

Interdisciplinary collaboration plays a vital role in advancing orofacial rehabilitation. The integration of expertise from prosthodontists, maxillofacial surgeons, material scientists, and biomedical engineers is crucial for developing innovative solutions that address both the functional and aesthetic needs of patients. This collaborative approach has led to groundbreaking developments in prosthetic design, surgical techniques, and material science.^[18] The adoption of eco-friendly materials and energy-efficient production methods is becoming increasingly important in reducing the environmental impact of healthcare. By developing sustainable practices, the field can align with global efforts to address environmental challenges while continuing to innovate and improve patient care.^[19]

These advancements signify a paradigm shift in orofacial rehabilitation, moving beyond traditional approaches to embrace a future where technology, biology, and patient-centered care converge. With the continued exploration of these new frontiers, the potential to restore not just function and aesthetics but also the dignity and quality of life for patients is greater than ever.^[20]

Current practices

Orofacial rehabilitation has evolved significantly over the decades, integrating a range of techniques, materials, and protocols to restore functionality and aesthetics for patients with orofacial deformities or damage. Conventional prosthetic approaches remain a cornerstone, employing techniques such as impression-making, casting, and manual customization to produce prosthetics that align with a patient's specific needs.^[21] These techniques have been augmented by digital workflows, including CAD/CAM systems and

3D printing technologies, which enhance precision and reduce fabrication time.^[10]

Surgical interventions, including reconstructive procedures and implant placements, have also advanced with the use of guided surgery and preoperative planning based on imaging technologies like CBCT and MRI. For materials, silicones and acrylics dominate in soft tissue and hard tissue prosthetics, respectively. Recent years have seen the adoption of high-performance polymers such as polyetheretherketone (PEEK) for their durability and biocompatibility. Adhesives and retention systems have also seen incremental improvements, allowing for better stability of maxillofacial prosthetics.^[22]

Rehabilitation protocols often extend beyond prosthetics to include physical therapy, speech therapy, and psychological support, ensuring a holistic approach to patient care. Despite these advancements, conventional methods are limited in addressing the complexities of individual cases, particularly in adapting to dynamic anatomical changes and achieving long-term success.

Challenges

While current practices have brought remarkable improvements, they face persistent challenges that hinder optimal outcomes.

- Many prosthetics and materials degrade over time due to mechanical wear, chemical exposure, or environmental factors. Frequent replacements or repairs are required, increasing costs and reducing patient satisfaction.
- While most modern materials are safe for clinical use, long-term biocompatibility issues can arise, including allergic reactions, tissue irritation, or integration failures.
- Achieving an exact match in color, texture, and translucency between prosthetics and natural tissues remains a significant

challenge. Even minor mismatches can lead to noticeable differences, affecting patient confidence and social acceptance.

- Many patients struggle to adapt to prosthetics due to discomfort, poor fit, or limited functionality. These issues can delay rehabilitation progress and reduce adherence to prescribed care.
- Patients with extensive trauma, congenital anomalies, or oncological resections often require highly customized solutions that go beyond the capabilities of conventional techniques.
- Advanced technologies and materials can be prohibitively expensive, limiting their availability to a broader population. This creates disparities in access to high-quality care.

The need to overcome these challenges has driven the development of innovative approaches and multidisciplinary collaborations in orofacial rehabilitation.^[18,20,21]

- Digital workflows, including AI-assisted planning and 3D printing, are paving the way for highly individualized prosthetic designs. These technologies allow for precise replication of anatomical features and the ability to accommodate dynamic changes in patient anatomy over time.
- Tissue engineering and stem cell research are shifting the focus from replacing to regenerating tissues. Scaffold-based approaches combined with biomaterials are being explored to encourage natural tissue growth, offering more sustainable and integrated solutions.
- The development of materials that mimic the mechanical, aesthetic, and biological properties of natural tissues is gaining traction. These include nanocomposites, smart polymers, and bioresorbable materials that enhance prosthetic performance and patient comfort.

- A growing emphasis on collaboration among prosthodontists, surgeons, biomedical engineers, and material scientists is fostering innovation. This multidisciplinary approach ensures that solutions are both clinically viable and technologically advanced.
- Advances in surgical technology, such as robotic-assisted procedures and bioactive implants, are making orofacial rehabilitation less invasive and more efficient, reducing recovery times and improving outcomes.
- Innovations in pigmentation technologies and texture replication are addressing the demand for prosthetics that are indistinguishable from natural tissues.
- The integration of sustainable materials and energy-efficient processes is gaining attention, reflecting a commitment to environmental responsibility in healthcare.

Innovative approaches in orofacial rehabilitation

Orofacial rehabilitation, a field rooted in restoring the vital functions and aesthetics of the oral and facial regions, is undergoing a transformative phase driven by cutting-edge innovations. These advancements are reshaping traditional practices and offering solutions that are more precise, personalized, and patient-centric. From groundbreaking technologies to novel materials and regenerative medicine, the future of orofacial rehabilitation lies in embracing these innovative approaches.^[12,15,16]

The integration of advanced technologies has revolutionized the way clinicians approach orofacial rehabilitation. Among the most transformative technologies, 3D printing has emerged as a game-changer in the creation of prosthetics and anatomical models. This technology allows for the rapid and accurate fabrication of custom prosthetics tailored to a patient's unique anatomy. Unlike traditional methods, which rely on manual craftsmanship,

3D printing provides unparalleled precision, enabling the recreation of intricate structures such as the contours of a face or the intricate details of intraoral frameworks. Anatomical models printed using high-resolution 3D printers also serve as invaluable tools for pre-surgical planning, allowing clinicians to simulate complex procedures and improve outcomes.^[17]

Computer-aided design and computer-aided manufacturing (CAD/CAM) systems have set a new standard in restorative dentistry and maxillofacial rehabilitation. These systems facilitate the design and production of highly accurate restorations, from crowns and bridges to full facial prosthetics. With the integration of CAD/CAM, clinicians can now streamline workflows, reduce errors, and significantly cut down production times. The ability to digitally design prosthetics ensures that every restoration is optimized for fit, functionality, and aesthetics, catering to the individual needs of each patient.^[9,10]

Advancements in material science have introduced a new generation of biomaterials designed to mimic natural tissues in structure and functionality. Materials that replicate the physical and biological properties of natural tissues are redefining prosthetic design. These biomimetic materials, such as hydrogels and bioactive ceramics, exhibit properties like elasticity, translucency, and thermal resistance that closely match human tissues. They not only improve the functional performance of prosthetics but also enhance their integration with the surrounding biological environment.^[13]

Biopolymers, derived from natural sources, are gaining popularity for their biocompatibility and sustainability. These materials, such as chitosan and polylactic acid, are being utilized in applications ranging from soft tissue prosthetics to biodegradable scaffolds for tissue regeneration. Nanotechnology is further augmenting these materials, with nanoparticles being

incorporated to improve strength, wear resistance, and antimicrobial properties. Nanocoatings on prosthetic surfaces, for example, reduce bacterial adhesion, minimizing the risk of infections and improving long-term outcomes.^[12,13]

The integration of regenerative medicine into orofacial rehabilitation marks a paradigm shift, focusing on the restoration of biological tissues rather than their replacement. Tissue engineering combines scaffolds, cells, and bioactive molecules to promote the regeneration of damaged or lost tissues. In orofacial applications, this approach is being used to develop engineered constructs for bone and soft tissue replacement. Bioengineered scaffolds, often fabricated using 3D printing, provide a framework that supports cell growth and vascularization, ensuring the formation of functional tissues.^[14]

Stem cells, with their unique ability to differentiate into various cell types, are at the forefront of regenerative strategies in orofacial rehabilitation. Mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) derived from sources such as bone marrow and adipose tissue have shown immense potential in promoting the repair and regeneration of hard and soft tissues. Clinical applications include the regeneration of periodontal tissues, alveolar bone, and even salivary glands. These therapies hold the promise of more natural and sustainable solutions, reducing the need for synthetic materials and invasive procedures.^[23] The true potential of these innovations lies in their integration, creating a comprehensive approach that combines technology, material science, and biology. The innovative approaches are not merely enhancing the existing practices but it redefines the orofacial rehabilitation. By embracing the convergence of technology, materials, and regenerative medicine, the research is unlocking the future of rehabilitation.

Transformative outcomes

Orofacial rehabilitation aims to restore more than just the physical appearance of affected regions. It aids to achieve holistic recovery, ensuring functional efficiency, emotional well-being, and an improved quality of life. Transformative outcomes in this field extend beyond conventional measures, focusing on patient-centered success and personalized functional rehabilitation.^[3]

One of the primary goals of orofacial rehabilitation is the restoration of critical functions such as speech, mastication, and facial aesthetics. Advances in technology, materials, and clinical approaches have significantly improved these outcomes. The restoration of speech and mastication plays a vital role in reintegrating patients into daily life, enabling effective communication and nutritional intake. Sophisticated prosthetic designs, incorporating anatomically precise structures, ensure proper articulation and chewing efficiency. Enhanced aesthetics, achieved through biomimetic materials and precision-engineered prosthetics, boost patient confidence and social acceptance, further enriching their quality of life.^[1,2]

Personalization lies at the core of transformative outcomes. Each patient presents a unique set of challenges, from varying anatomical structures to specific functional requirements. Digital workflows, including CAD/CAM systems and 3D printing, enable clinicians to design and fabricate solutions that address these individual needs. Technologies like virtual surgical planning (VSP) allow precise preoperative customization of prosthetics and implants, ensuring compatibility with the patient's anatomy. This tailored approach minimizes complications, reduces recovery time, and improves the overall success rate of interventions.^[10]

In the modern paradigm of healthcare, the measure of success extends beyond clinical efficacy to include patient satisfaction,

emotional well-being, and sustained outcomes. Transformative outcomes prioritize the patient's perspective, ensuring that interventions align with their expectations and lifestyle. Enhanced comfort, ease of use, and aesthetics contribute to higher levels of satisfaction. For example, lightweight materials and improved retention mechanisms for maxillofacial prosthetics ensure that patients can wear their devices comfortably for extended periods without compromising functionality. Psychological support, integrated into the rehabilitation process, helps patients adapt to their new prosthetics and regain confidence in social settings.^[9]

Durability is a critical aspect of successful orofacial rehabilitation. Advances in biomaterials, such as high-performance polymers and nanocomposites, have extended the lifespan of prosthetics and implants. These materials resist wear, degradation, and microbial colonization, ensuring long-term functionality. Similarly, innovations like bioactive coatings promote tissue integration and reduce the risk of implant failure, contributing to more predictable and enduring outcomes.^[12]

The focus on transformative outcomes ensures that orofacial rehabilitation is not merely a clinical endeavor but a life-changing experience for patients. By integrating functional efficiency with aesthetic precision and prioritizing patient satisfaction, the field continues to redefine the possibilities of rehabilitation, offering solutions that restore not just physical attributes but also the dignity and quality of life for individuals affected by orofacial conditions.^[17]

Clinical Implications

Innovations in orofacial rehabilitation are transforming the theoretical and research-driven advancements into practical, patient-centered solutions. To maximize the benefits of these advancements, their integration into routine clinical practice and the fostering of

interdisciplinary collaboration are paramount.^[5,7,20,21]

The adoption of groundbreaking technologies and methodologies into everyday clinical workflows has the potential to redefine treatment standards.

- Cutting-edge technologies such as 3D printing and CAD/CAM systems, once considered niche, are now increasingly affordable and accessible. Their integration into clinical setups allows clinicians to deliver precise, rapid, and cost-effective solutions.
- Innovations have made it possible to develop personalized treatment protocols tailored to individual patient needs. Digital tools, including intraoral scanners and virtual design platforms, provide real-time data that can be used to customize prosthetics and treatment strategies.

To ensure consistent and effective outcomes, standardized clinical protocols need to be established for the application of advanced techniques and materials.

Future Directions

The future of orofacial rehabilitation holds immense promise, driven by continuous advancements in technology, research, and material science. Several key areas of development are poised to reshape the field, enhancing treatment outcomes and patient care. These include innovations in research, sustainability, and the increasing focus on personalized treatments.^[15,16]

Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) are revolutionizing healthcare, and their potential applications in orofacial rehabilitation are particularly exciting. These technologies enable the processing and analysis of vast amounts of patient data, which can significantly improve diagnostic accuracy and treatment planning. AI can help identify patterns in anatomical variations, predict treatment outcomes, and recommend

personalized prosthetic solutions. Machine learning algorithms can be integrated with 3D imaging and scanning technologies to automatically adapt treatment plans, suggesting the most effective rehabilitation approaches based on historical patient data and current conditions. The use of AI in patient management could streamline workflows, reduce human error, and ultimately lead to more efficient and precise rehabilitation outcomes.^[10,11,17,18]

Imaging technology is central to the precision of diagnosis and the development of individualized treatment plans. Innovations such as 3D imaging, cone beam computed tomography (CBCT), and functional MRI provide detailed, multidimensional views of the orofacial structures, enabling clinicians to evaluate the exact extent of defects or deformities. These technologies allow for accurate mapping of soft and hard tissue structures, improving the fit and function of prosthetics. In addition, the integration of advanced imaging with virtual reality (VR) can help in visualizing complex anatomical models for pre-surgical planning and simulation. As these techniques evolve, they promise even greater precision in diagnosing issues and monitoring rehabilitation progress, allowing for personalized and highly tailored interventions.^[15-17]

The world becomes increasingly aware of environmental issues, the focus on sustainability within healthcare is growing. In orofacial rehabilitation, the development and use of eco-friendly materials are gaining attention. Bio-based resins, recyclable metals, and sustainable ceramics are emerging as viable alternatives to conventional materials that contribute to environmental waste. Furthermore, advancements in biodegradable polymers are encouraging the design of prosthetics that do not contribute to long-term pollution. Sustainable manufacturing methods, such as 3D printing with eco-conscious materials, also minimize waste by

enabling precise fabrication with reduced material usage. In addition, sustainable clinical practices—such as reducing energy consumption in prosthetic laboratories and using digital workflows that reduce the need for physical models—offer a more environmentally responsible approach to orofacial rehabilitation. By adopting these practices, the field can help ensure ethical and eco-conscious treatment options for patients while mitigating its environmental impact.^[12,13,19]

Personalization of treatment is becoming a cornerstone of modern healthcare, and orofacial rehabilitation is no exception. The future of personalized rehabilitation may increasingly rely on genetic and epigenetic information to predict patient-specific responses to treatments and materials. Genetic profiling could provide valuable insights into how patients heal, their propensity for tissue rejection, or their susceptibility to complications following prosthetic placement. Additionally, epigenetic factors—such as environmental influences that modify gene expression—could help predict how patients will respond to biomaterials or regenerative therapies, allowing for more tailored and effective interventions. For example, understanding a patient's genetic predisposition to bone density or tissue regeneration could lead to customized prosthetic designs or the use of specialized regenerative therapies that promote healing and integration. Furthermore, insights into how genetic factors interact with external stimuli (such as diet or lifestyle) may also guide the selection of specific rehabilitation materials or therapies that align with the patient's biological makeup. The incorporation of such personalized approaches could result in enhanced success rates, improved functionality, and longer-lasting outcomes for patients.^[6,10,11,12,15]

Conclusion

Innovative approaches in orofacial rehabilitation hold immense transformative potential, reshaping patient care, treatment outcomes, and overall quality of life. Advancements in technology, materials, and collaborative practices are driving this evolution, with tools like 3D printing, CAD/CAM systems, and AI-driven planning, alongside biomimetic materials, regenerative medicine, and sustainable practices, making the future increasingly personalized, efficient, and environmentally conscious. These innovations enhance both the functional and emotional well-being of patients by offering tailored, high-quality prosthetic solutions. Moving forward, researchers and clinicians must embrace emerging trends, fostering collaboration to push the boundaries of the field. The goal is to develop more effective, sustainable, and patient-centered solutions that redefine orofacial rehabilitation and set new standards of care.

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AI assistance technology was utilized

References

1. Sailer I. Reflections on future research directions in prosthodontics. *Int J Prosthodont.* 2024 Nov 22;37(6):604.
2. Gilbert RW. Reconstruction of the oral cavity; past, present and future. *Oral Oncol.* 2020 Sep;108:104683.
3. Karnik AP, Chhajer H, Venkatesh SB. Transforming prosthodontics and oral implantology using robotics and artificial intelligence. *Front Oral Health.* 2024 Jul 29;5:1442100.

4. Quadri P, McMullen C. Oral cavity reconstruction. *Otolaryngol Clin North Am.* 2023 Aug;56(4):671-686.
5. Karnik AP, Chhajer H, Venkatesh SB. Transforming prosthodontics and oral implantology using robotics and artificial intelligence. *Front Oral Health.* 2024 Jul 29;5:1442100.
6. Joda T, Zitzmann NU. Personalized workflows in reconstructive dentistry-current possibilities and future opportunities. *Clin Oral Investig.* 2022 Jun;26(6):4283-4290.
7. Schwendicke F, Samek W, Krois J. Artificial intelligence in dentistry: chances and challenges. *J Dent Res.* 2020 Jul;99(7):769-774.
8. Jeong M, Radomski K, Lopez D, Liu JT, Lee JD, Lee SJ. Materials and applications of 3d printing technology in dentistry: aAn overview. *Dent J (Basel).* 2023 Dec 19;12(1):1.
9. Singi SR, Sathe S, Reche AR, Sibal A, Mantri N. Extended arm of precision in prosthodontics: artificial intelligence. *Cureus.* 2022 Nov 1;14(11):e30962.
10. Alghazzawi TF. Advancements in CAD/CAM technology: options for practical implementation. *J Prosthodont Res.* 2016 Apr;60(2):72-84.
11. Alyami MH. The applications of 3D-printing technology in prosthodontics: a review of the current literature. *Cureus.* 2024 Sep 3;16(9):e68501.
12. Saeed F, Muhammad N, Khan AS, Sharif F, Rahim A, Ahmad P, Irfan M. Prosthodontics dental materials: From conventional to unconventional. *Mater Sci Eng C Mater Biol Appl.* 2020 Jan;106:110167.
13. Singer L, Fouda A, Bourauel C. Biomimetic approaches and materials in restorative and regenerative dentistry: review article. *BMC Oral Health.* 2023 Feb 16;23(1):105.
14. Zafar MS, Amin F, Fareed MA, Ghabbani H, Riaz S, Khurshid Z, Kumar N. Biomimetic aspects of restorative dentistry biomaterials. *Biomimetics (Basel).* 2020 Jul 15;5(3):34.
15. Bonny T, Al Nassan W, Obaideen K, Al Mallahi MN, Mohammad Y, El-Damanhoury HM. Contemporary role and applications of artificial intelligence in dentistry. *F1000Res.* 2023 Sep 20;12:1179.
16. Ahmed N, Abbasi MS, Zuberi F, Qamar W, Halim MSB, Maqsood A, Alam MK. Artificial intelligence techniques: analysis, application, and outcome in dentistry-a systematic review. *Biomed Res Int.* 2021 Jun 22;2021:9751564.
17. Tian Y, Chen C, Xu X, Wang J, Hou X, Li K, Lu X, Shi H, Lee ES, Jiang HB. A review of 3d printing in dentistry: technologies, affecting factors, and applications. *Scanning.* 2021 Jul 17;2021:9950131.
18. Kaku M. Prosthodontics: A multidisciplinary field in dentistry. *J Prosthodont Res.* 2016 Jul;60(3):143-4.
19. Tawade SU, Dhamande MM, Dubey SA, Sathe S, Selukar MS, Pathak A. Sustainable dentistry: a comprehensive review of the recycling techniques for gypsum products in prosthodontics. *Cureus.* 2024 Mar 12;16(3):e55997.
20. Chander NG, Gopi A. Trends and future perspectives of 3D printing in prosthodontics. *Med J Armed Forces India.* 2024 Jul-Aug;80(4):399-403..
21. Carlsson GE, Omar R. Trends in prosthodontics. *Med Princ Pract.* 2006;15(3):167-79.
22. Alexakou E, Damanaki M, Zoidis P, Bakiri E, Mouzis N, Smidt G, Kourtis S. PEEK high performance polymers: a review of properties and clinical applications in prosthodontics and restorative dentistry. *Eur J Prosthodont Restor Dent.* 2019 Aug 29;27(3):113-121.

23. Shah P, Aghazadeh M, Rajasingh S, Dixon D, Jain V, Rajasingh J. Stem cells in regenerative dentistry: Current understanding and future directions. J Oral Biosci. 2024 Jun;66(2):288-299.